

Influence of Intellectual Capital, Government Support and Entrepreneurial Leadership on Organisational Performance

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Abstract

Background: There are inconsistent research results regarding the role of intellectual capital (IC), entrepreneurial leadership (EL), and government support (GS) in organisational performance (OP).

Objective: This study examined the role of Intellectual Capital (IC), entrepreneurial leadership (EL), and government support (GS) on organisational performance (OP).

Methodology: This study used a descriptive survey to achieve its aim. The sampling technique used was snowball sampling, with 87 private universities participating and completing the questionnaire. The analysis was conducted using SEMPLS with outer model testing, inner model testing, and hypothesis testing.

Results: The research results show that IC and EL have no effect on organisational performance. However, the IC measures, namely human capital (HC), relational capital (RC), structural capital

(SC), technological capital (TC), and spiritual capital (SPC), have a significant impact on IC. In addition, the seven roles of EL show a positive, meaningful, or significant direction towards performance. The variable of government support (GS) has a positive direction and has a significant impact on organisational performance (OP).

Conclusion: IC is an element that forms a competitive, effective, and efficient strategic advantage, while HC and SC have a low contribution to IC in PTS. The variable of government support (GS) in private higher education institutions is also very important.

Unique contribution: An outer model test was conducted in two stages on the dimensions of the IC variable in the EL role, revealing the dimensions of the variable that have a strong relationship with the latent variable.

Key Recommendation: Several factors that may influence the research outcomes, the IC element is intellectual agility. Next, this factor can be explored further to understand the existing relationships by expanding the survey to other government areas to compare findings and understand the weight of the reference context where IC has multidimensionality and the role of EL.

Keywords: Leadership entrepreneurship, intellectual capital, performance organisation

Introduction

Research on Intellectual Capital (IC) has interacted with various elements, both financial and non-financial. Samples, methods, analysis techniques, and empirical results vary, as shown by research that reveals the Structural Capital (SC) variable does not affect non-financial performance. Research by Hanifah et al. (2021) and Pigola et al. (2021) revealed that, besides capital structure, relational capital also does not affect non-financial performance (innovation). In financial performance, SC has no effect (Izzo et al., 2021). According to Soewarno and Tjahjadi (2020), Human Capital (HC) does not affect performance. Abualoush et al. (2018) note that Technology Capital (TC) has no effect, while Barkat et al. (2018) and Khalique and Abdul (2020) reveal that technology has an influence, whereas Spiritual Capital (SCP) has no effect on performance. Unlike the results of (Ur Rehman et al., 2021; Mahaputra et al., 2021), which indicate that IC, consisting of elements HC, SC, RC, and TC affects OP. A study of Singla et al. (2021) revealed that quality of life is positively influenced by spiritual intelligence.

Dynamic environmental changes and increasingly intense competition suggest that unique leadership is required to position organisations to capture opportunities and enhance their ability to create the necessary variations in a highly unpredictable environment. Performance is the result of the leader's role in managing intellectual resources, and it is significant to the organisation's success or failure. Research findings (Alrowwad et al., 2020) also state that leadership is a management function of every organisation, and strong leadership helps organisations enhance their competitiveness. Leadership refers to the relationship formed between a leader and their followers, with the leader directing the behaviour of their followers.

EL leadership style has a positive relationship with organisational effectiveness, prioritising opportunities and resources that help people and organisations to continue working synergistically to achieve common goals. To seize opportunities is one of the roles of EL (Gupta et al., 2004). The

next role of EL, which is building commitment and determining gravity, requires the leader's own leadership ability to motivate others and mobilise resources to facilitate change.

Previous research has revealed that entrepreneurial orientation and EL have a positive impact on performance (Paudel, 2019; Sawaeen & Ali, 2020; Sarabi et al., 2020). However, some findings contradict the research (Paudel, 2019; Sawaeen & Ali, 2020; Sarabi et al., 2020). The influence of innovation on performance is not significant. Moreover, Aryatib et al. (2021) stated that innovation is not significant to performance. The research results on the role of EL, such as facilitating the acceptance of group goals and offering intellectual stimulation, idea selection, development, and diffusion, have a negative relationship with OP and innovation (Aryatib et al., 2021). Furthermore, research by Anggriani and Kistyanto (2021) also reinforces that EL indirectly affects performance.

Several studies reveal that intangible capital (IC) components, such as Structural Capital (SC), Human Capital (HC), Relational Capital (RC), and Technological Capital (TC), do not significantly affect financial or non-financial performance. However, other studies show contradictory results, indicating that IC has a positive impact on organisational performance. Additionally, there are limitations in the exploration of broader dimensions of IC.

Some studies claim that EL has a favourable impact on organisational performance (OP), while others show an inconsequential or even detrimental influence on innovation and OP. This suggests a lack of consistency in recognising the function of entrepreneurial leadership (EL) in impacting organisational performance (OP), particularly in the context of Indonesian private institutions. Furthermore, the role of the government as an external force has not been thoroughly investigated. As a result, there is a need for a study to understand better the relationship between IC, EL, and the role of the government in OP, particularly in the context of Indonesian private institutions confronting competitive and dynamic environmental difficulties.

This research aims to fill the existing gap by analysing the roles of IC, EL, and government support towards OP in PTS in Indonesia. Thus, this research is expected to provide theoretical and practical contributions in developing strategies to enhance OP through the optimisation of IC, effective implementation of EL, and relevant government support.

Development Hypothesis and Conceptual Framework

1. IC on OP

Organizations operate based on vision and mission, so most of their decisions and operations are structured according to these principles, which are realised through strategic planning involving HC, SC, and RC, referred to as intangible resources. HC refers to the collective knowledge possessed by employees within an organisation. In the context of human resources in higher education, this is explicitly recognised as knowledge. IC is defined specifically for lecturers and researchers in terms of teaching capacity and research competency. SC is described as an organisation's capacity to carry out its everyday operational processes. SC's performance in PT is indicated by intrinsic values such as intellectual property recognition, technology development, patents, licenses, publications, databases, bibliographic sources, and management systems, which include accreditation and certification procedures.

The above processes are supported by technology, which actively engages as a transfer object, representing the trinity of equipment, worker competence, and technology. At the same time, SCP is a combination of religious and ethical values within the organisation (Khalique et al. 2020). Revealed at least six prominent characteristics: namely, wealth, faith and trust, values, virtues, vision, and benefits. SCP enriches aspects of life such as instilling motivation in living and working. The elements of IC are interconnected, having a broad impact on performance according to the research findings of Pigola et al. (2021), which state that IC influences OP

H1 IC has an effect on OP

H1.1 HC has an effect on IC

H1.2 SC has an effect on IC

H1.3 RC has an effect on IC

H1.4 TC has an effect on IC

H1.5 SCP has an effect on IC

2. EL on OP

KW is a response to the current survival and achievement of the organisation. Leadership with high risk tolerance, a preference for innovative activities, and a high level of proactive exemplary behaviour will positively impact OP. Ur Rehman et al. (2020) added that entrepreneurial competence for organisations plays an important role in improving organisational performance. Paudel's findings (2019), Imran and Aldaas's (2020), Sarabi et al.'s (2020), Sawaeen and Ali's (2020), and Alrowwad et al.'s (2019) revealed that EL has a positive and significant impact on OP.

H2 EL has a positive effect on OP.

H2.1 Framing Challenge (MT) influences EL

H2.2 Commitment to building (MK) influences EL

H2.3 Underwriter (PE) influences EL

H2.4 Absorption uncertainty (MAK) influences EL

H2.5 Definition of gravity (MG) influences EL

H2.6 Innovation Exploration (IE) influences EL

H2.7 Exploitative Innovation (IEKS) influences EL

3. Government Support (GS) on OP

The research findings (Karnsomdee, 2021) indicate that government policies have both direct and indirect impacts on OP. The government must establish public policies that are popular, innovative, and competitive to support change and turn those policies into actions.

H3: GS influences OP.

Based on the conceptual and hypothesis framework, the model is illustrated as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Research Model

Methodology

The type of research is fundamental, with the unit of analysis being the institution. The population consists of 205 private universities (PTS) in South Sumatra, Lampung, Bangka Belitung, and Bengkulu, with 87 PTS willing to be sampled to answer the questionnaire filled out by structural officials of faculties/programs. The sampling technique used is non-probability sampling, specifically snowball sampling, with the distribution of the questionnaire from November 2021 to July 2022. The analysis technique uses SEMPLS data analysis, and the PLS path model consists of two elements. First, the Measurement Model Test (Outer Model) is used to determine the model's validity and dependability. Second, the Structural Model Test (inner Model) evaluates the R-squared value, which represents the model's goodness-of-fit. Hypothesis testing is then performed to determine the statistical significance of the influence between variables by assessing the parameter coefficient values, T-statistic significance values, and P-values. If the p-value is low (usually below the specified significance level, such as 0.05), then the influence between variables is considered statistically significant. Meanwhile, the t-statistic value (t-value) measures the extent of the difference between the estimated parameter (path coefficient) and zero. If the t-value is large and statistically significant (small p-value), then the influence between variables is considered significant.

Research Results

Validity and Reliability Test

The Indicators are considered valid if they have a recommended standard loading value of more than 0.7. The indicators that were removed are the second-order variables for the Spiritual Capital

The latent variables IC towards OP and IC towards SCP are the only ones with values greater than -1, as seen in Figure 2 above. All other variables, however, have satisfied the conventional value requirements. If the f Square value, which is used to test for influence between variables, is less than 0.02 then there is no influence. A moderate influence is indicated by a f Square value between 0.02 and 0.14, and a strong influence is indicated by a value between 0.15 and 0.35.

Table 1. *f Square Test*

	EL	OP	IC
EL		0.034	
OP			
GS		0.731	
IC		0.009	
HC			0.793
RC			2,478
SPC			0.052
SC			8,649
TC			9,353
IE	9,041		
IEKSP	3,244		
MAK	10,184		
MG	5,773		
MK	10,879		
PE	8,010		
MT	3,036		

Source: Smart PLS Data Processing Results 2022

According to Table 1, the f-square test reveals that the latent variables and constructs have a considerable impact on IC with values of 0.0793, 2.478, 8.649, and 9.353 for HC, RC, SC, and TC, and a small impact with a value of 0.053 for SCP. The role of EL towards OP has a f square value of 0.034, indicating a minor effect, whereas IC towards OP has a f square value of 0.009, indicating no effect. The findings of the inner model evaluation are displayed below in Table 2 R Square.

Table 2. R Square Test

	R Square	Adjusted R Squared
OP	0.434	0.407
HC	0.442	0.434
RC	0.713	0.708
SPC	0.050	0.035
SC	0.896	0.895
TC	0.903	0.902
IE	0.900	0.899
IEKSP	0.764	0.761
MAK	0.911	0.909
MG	0.852	0.850
MK	0.916	0.915
FE	0.889	0.887
MT	0.752	0.748

Source: 2022 Data Processing Results

According to Table 2, the OP variable is strong because the R Square value exceeds 0.75. OP, HC, and SPC are appropriate models for the studied influence factors, with SRMR values < 0.10 (0.086).

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing uses an alpha statistic of 5% and a t-statistic value of 1.96, the criteria for accepting/rejecting the hypothesis are to accept H_a and reject H_0 if the p-value > 0.005 (b) reject H_0 and accept H_a if the p-value < 0.005. The results of the hypothesis in Table 3 below.

Table 3. Direct Test Results

Hypothesis	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P Value
IC -> OP	-0.134	-0.127	0.174	0.771	0.441
IC -> HC	0.665	0.670	0.054	12,216	0,000
IC -> RC	0.844	0.845	0.033	25,664	0,000
IC -> SC	0.947	0.947	0.013	72,821	0,000
IC -> TC	0.950	0.950	0.012	77,008	0,000
IC -> SPC	-0.223	-0.230	0.106	2,107	0.036

Hypothesis	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P Value
EL -> OP	0.259	0.253	0.183	1,418	0.157
EL -> MT	0.867	0.866	0.034	25,867	0,000
EL-> MK	0.957	0.957	0.010	91,490	0,000
EL-> MG	0.923	0.920	0.034	27,422	0,000
EL -> PE	0.943	0.944	0.013	70,112	0,000
EL -> MAK	0.954	0.956	0.012	79,877	0,000
EL-> IEKSP	0.874	0.874	0.034	25,950	0,000
EL -> IE	0.949	0.949	0.015	62,658	0,000
KP -> OP	0.691	0.693	0.062	11,095	0,000

Source: 2022 Data Processing Results

Table 3 describes the results of hypothesis testing based on the requirements.

Table 4. Research Hypothesis Results

Hypothesis	Information
IC -> OP	Rejected
HC -> IC	supported
SC -> IC	supported
RC -> IC	supported
TC -> IC	supported
SPC -> IC	supported
EL -> OP	Rejected
MT -> EL	supported
MK -> EL	supported
PE -> EL	supported
MAK -> EL	supported
MG -> EL	supported
ID -> EL	supported
IEKSP -> EL	supported
GS -> OP	supported

Source: 2022 Data Processing Results

Discussion

Since the findings contradict the findings of Pigola et al. (2021), which demonstrate that IC significantly improves OP, Hypothesis H1 is rejected. However, those who claim that IC does not affect OP corroborate the findings of this investigation. Additionally, according to the RBV theory, a combination of intangible and tangible resources is necessary to attain superior competitive and sustainable strength; these resources must be rare, valuable, difficult to replicate, and irreplaceable. Superior competitive organisations possess capabilities, processes, characteristics or attributes, information, and knowledge that enable the organisation to execute strategies effectively and efficiently. IC refers to the value of knowledge, skills, and intellectual abilities possessed by individuals or organisations. In the context of private universities, although IC holds significant value, several factors can more dominantly influence the performance of a university. First, a PTS performance is influenced by a variety of factors, including its reputation throughout time, efficient management, successful marketing campaigns, and availability of sufficient funding. Second, the performance of private colleges may also be impacted by outside variables, including laws, the state of the economy, and rivalry with other academic institutions. This investigation supports the results of Abualoush et al. (2018). IC can affect OP indirectly in addition to directly, albeit this is not always the case. This indicates that other factors, including competitive advantage, strategy, innovation, management control systems, and information sharing, act as mediators of IC (Barkat et al., 2018; Hanifah et al., 2021; Khalique & Abdul, 2020). They were designated as IC Respondents based on the researchers' observations at a number of PTS. become an appealing competitive advantage that gives stakeholders a sense of the higher education institution's overall excellence. Professors, head lecturers, and master's degree-holding lecturers are recognised as knowledgeable sources at their university, demonstrating the high calibre and dependability of their institution.

Hypotheses H1.1, H1.2, H1.3, H1.4, and H1.5 are accepted. Hypothesis H1.1 that HC affects IC is accepted. These results support the research of Izzo (2022). HC is not the main element among the five components of IC that influence it, unlike the study mapping results with different settings and objects, where HC becomes the main influencing factor of IC. The researcher suspects that some respondents believe that PTS is the initial place where knowledge emerges, making it a natural occurrence. Human resources, especially university lecturers, are explicitly like knowledge. The forms of HC include training, experience, assessment, intelligence, relationships, and individual insights. This form of HC is a significant part of the activities carried out by the company. So, these elements of HC do not have a significant impact on IC.

The acceptance of hypotheses H1.3 and H1.5 contradicts the findings of Khalique and Abdul's (2020) study, which defines SCP as a combination of dimensions that lead to spirituality in humans, comprising religiosity, morality, transcendence capacity, sanctity of life, altruism, and creativity. Hypothesis H2, which claims that EL's contribution to PTS performance is positive but not substantial, is therefore rejected. These findings are somewhat at odds with those of Imran and Aldaas (2020) and Ur Rehman et al. (2021), who found that entrepreneurial leadership significantly and favorably affects OP. According to Alrowwad et al. (2020), effective leadership is one of the elements in preserving competitive advantage.

Hypothesis H2.1, H2.2, H2.3, H2.4, H2.5, H2.6, and H2.7 that the seven roles influence EL is accepted and shows a positive direction. For example, MK, this role sets realistic goals for PTS that need to be improved to achieve the vision and mission in the statutes, strategic plan documents and so on. MT devotes attention to the vision and instils trust with others to achieve the desired goals. PE by seeking support from others for diplomatic bargaining to achieve goals. Roles of MK, MAK, MT, IE, PE, MG, and IEKSP in EL. Hypothesis H3 is accepted, and the results of this study align with Karnsomdee (2021), proving that government policy has a significant relationship with OP. In this study, there is a role where EL is used as a second order, but the researcher did not specify that role.

Conclusion, Implications and Limitations

Based on the research results above, IC does not have a significant influence on OP. The five tested elements of IC have an influence, but HC does not. The main elements of IC formation in PTS are made possible by the organizational character, as well as SCP. This implies that HC is undoubtedly a characteristic of PT as a vessel of knowledge; in addition to serving as a bearer of knowledge and technology, it must also be able to educate people so that they can practice all the talents and potential they possess. However, the elements of RC, SC, and TC influence IC. The role of EL towards OP is not influential; however, seven of its roles show a positive and significant direction towards EL. The variable of government role in PTS, represented by the GS, has a positive direction and significantly affects OP.

Practical implications for PTS can be drawn from the results of this empirical study, which show that the role of EL in PTS does not have a significant impact. PTS must not forget the primary purpose of establishing a university, as outlined in Law No. 12 of 2012, by considering the initially negative sample value. The results of this study can also serve as input for PTS as business entities to provide knowledge to lecturers, as they will be the ones to take on leadership roles (structural positions) in the PTS. Furthermore, the Ministry of Education and Culture can expand the government's role in improving the performance of PTS, considering that the GS is directly involved in the development of PTS in their respective regions.

This study has several limitations, including the following: first, the uneven distribution of respondents has not yet met the researcher's expectations, which may limit the generalizability of the anticipated empirical results. Respondents were chosen by the leaders of each PTS, allowing the author to collect focused data. Since IC does not affect performance, it is critical to do an additional study and expand or develop the variable Intellectual Agility, which can indirectly link IC to PTS performance.

References

- Abualoush, S., Masa'deh, R., Bataineh, K., & Alrowwad, A. (2018). The role of knowledge management process and intellectual capital as intermediary variable between knowledge management. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Information, Knowledge, and Management*, 13, 279–309. <https://doi.org/10.28945/4088>
- Alrowwad, A., Abualoush, S. H., & Masa'deh, R. (2020). Innovation and intellectual capital as intermediary variables among transformational leadership, transactional leadership, and organizational performance. *Journal of Management Development*, 39(2), 196–222. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JMD-02-2019-0062>

- Anggriani, Y. Y., & Kistyanto, A. (2021). The influence of entrepreneurial leadership on the performance of MSMEs in Surabaya city through innovation. *Journal of Economics and Finance*, 5(3), 407–427. <https://doi.org/10.24034/j25485024.y2021.v5.i3.4534>
- Barkat, W., Beh, L. S., Ahmed, A., & Ahmed, R. (2018). Impact of intellectual capital on innovation capability and organizational performance: An empirical investigation. *Serbian Journal of Management*, 13(2), 365–379. <https://doi.org/10.5937/sjm13-16997>
- Gupta, V., MacMillan, I. C., & Surie, G. (2004). Entrepreneurial leadership: developing and measuring a cross-cultural construct. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 19(2), 241–260. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0883-9026\(03\)00040-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0883-9026(03)00040-5)
- Hanifah, H., Abd Halim, N., Vafaei-Zadeh, A., & Nawaser, K. (2021). Effect of intellectual capital and entrepreneurial orientation on innovation performance of manufacturing SMEs: Mediating role of knowledge sharing. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 23, 1175–1198. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIC-06-2020-0186>
- Imran, R., & Aldaas, R. E. (2020). Entrepreneurial leadership: A missing link between perceived organizational support and organizational performance. *World Journal of Entrepreneurship, Management and Sustainable Development*, 16(4), 377–388. <https://doi.org/10.1108/WJEMSD-10-2019-0077>
- Izzo, F., Tomnyuk, V., & Lombardo, R. (2021). 4.0 Digital transition and human capital: Evidence from the Italian Fintech Market. *International Journal of Manpower*, 43(4), 910–925. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJM-04-2021-0255>
- Karnsomdee, Committeeman. (2021). The effects of government policy on organizational performance of provincial administrative organizations: mediating role of public entrepreneurship. *F1000Research*, 10:794. doi: 10.12688/f1000research.55080.1
- Khalique, M., & Abdul, J. (2020). Intellectual capital in tourism SMEs in Azad Jammu and Kashmir. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 21(3), 333–355. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIC-11-2018-0206>
- Mahaputra, I. N. K. A., Wiagustini, N. L. P., Yadnyana, I. K., & Artini, N. L. G. S. (2021). Organization behavior, intellectual capital, and performance: A case study of microfinance institutions in Indonesia. *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 8(4), 549–561. <https://doi.org/10.13106/jafeb.2021>
- Paudel, S. (2019). Entrepreneurial leadership and business performance: Effect of organizational innovation and environmental dynamism. *South Asian Journal of Business Studies*, 8(3), 348–369. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SAJBS-11-2018-0136>
- Pigola, A., De Santi, P. V., da Costa, P. R., & Storopoli, J. (2021). Intellectual capital on performance: A meta-analysis study enhancing a new perspective of the components. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 23(6), 1379–1403. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIC-01-2021-0025>
- Sarabi, A., Froese, F. J., Chng, D. H. M., & Meyer, K. E. (2020). Entrepreneurial leadership and MNE subsidiary performance: The moderating role of subsidiary context. *International Business Review*, 29(3), Article 101672. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ibusrev.2020.101672>
- Soewarno, Noorlailie, and Bambang Tjahjadi. (2020). Measures that matter: An empirical investigation of intellectual capital and financial performance of banking firms in Indonesia. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 21(6), 1085–1106. doi: 10.1108/JIC-09-2019-0225.

- Sawaeen, F. A. A., & Ali, K. A. M. (2020). The impact of entrepreneurial leadership and learning orientation on organizational performance of SMEs: the mediating role of innovation capacity. *Management Science Letters*, 10(2), 369–380. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.msl.2019.8.033>
- Singla, H., Mehta, M. D., & Mehta, P. (2021). Modeling spiritual intelligence on quality of work life of college teachers: A mediating role of psychological capital. *International Journal of Quality and Service Sciences*, 13(3), 341–358. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJQSS-07-2020-0108>
- Ur Rehman, S., Elrehail, H., Alsaad, A., & Bhatti, A. (2021). Intellectual capital and innovative performance: A mediation-moderation perspective. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*. 23(5), 998-1024. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIC-04-2020-0109>